

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“FURRY LOVE”

They say humans are capable of loving deeply.

It shows in their eyes, which glisten upon seeing the things they love and care for delicately. Just like those wrapped in fur, they greet you at doorways, in narrow alleys, and even along strange streets that have never felt like home.

A human's good intentions are enough for them to feel a sense of comfort, a refuge that lies in between.

They, too, are capable of loving and being loved.

They are creatures that cling to your presence, following you around as if you alone hold their whole world.

It is a quiet sorrow, knowing they find safety only in hearts that refuse cruelty.

Let us be gentle, for they are like us.

Dogs are our companions.

They bring light and joy to days when the world feels too rushed and heavy.

They may not understand life the way we do, but they show us how to love simply and find comfort in the smallest moments.

In their presence, even the hardest days feel a little more like home as we, too, are their home.